

Milestone: M2.2 Draft policies and best practice guidelines

Lead Participant:

BBMRI-ERIC

Author:

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Due:

30 Sep 2021

Date Of Completion:

26 Nov 2021

Means of Verification

Policy on [Incidental Findings](#) (IF) incl. [background](#)
Policy on [feedback provision of general research results](#)
Policy [on special \(vulnerable\) subjects](#)
Policy on consent (jointly with task 2.4; see link under Milestone M2.4)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes
Extensive discussion with 1+MG WG2 delayed the milestone as approval was related to 1+MG WG2 scheduling of meetings
IF policy had WG2 approval in September, the other three policies in November with subsequent submission to the 1+MG Group meeting (general research results, vulnerable subjects) and transfer to task 2.4 for further integration

Project participants & others

Policy on Incidental Findings: BBMRI-NL
Policy on feedback provision of general research results: BBMRI-NL
Policy on special (vulnerable) subjects: BBMRI-LV
Policy on consent: ECRIN (with UNILU / task 2.4)
Contributions all to all policies by WP2 / 1+MG WG2 members in meetings & workshops

Next action steps

The first three policies are under revision following input by the signatory countries and re-submitted for provisional approval.
The policy on consent is already integrated and will be further pursued with the “Transparency and Consent Policy” in task 2.4

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